

Building the future of bioinformatics with Nextflow

Technical innovation, community engagement,
and career development opportunities

September 19

Agenda

01. What is **Nextflow** and how does it help?
02. **nf-core** tools and best practices
03. Getting **started**, getting **help** and engaging with the **community**
04. Seqera **Platform**: Where Nextflow runs best
05. Upcoming **events**
06. **Q&A**

01.

What is **Nextflow**
and how does it help?

What's the problem?

Modern data analysis is a lot of work

- Big pile of data that needs to be processed
- Many different command-line tools
- Heterogeneous compute requirements
- Processing needs to be automated and reproducible

What's the problem?

Modern data analysis is a lot of work

What are your options?

Choose a tool wisely...

Old-school scripts

Bash, Python etc

First-gen workflow systems

Galaxy (XML + web GUI),
Snakemake (Python)

Next-gen workflow languages

Nextflow, WDL, CWL

Next-gen workflow languages

Developed from the ground up to express reproducible scientific workflows

Nextflow

Groovy DSL
+ Execution engine

WDL

Bash-like DSL
Separate engines
(Cromwell, miniWDL)

CWL

YAML + JSON
Separate engines
(Toil, Arvados, etc)

Nextflow is the fastest growing workflow framework

Google Scholar citation counts for bioinformatics workflow management systems.

Sum of citations of the major publications of Galaxy, Nextflow, and Snakemake between 2018 and 2023

Nextflow skills are in high demand

Required Skills:

- 3+ years of recent hands-on bioinformatics algorithms
- 3+ years of Python, R, or Java development experience being done with bioinformatics
- Experience with **Nextflow** bioinformatics frameworks and libraries

Requirements:

- PhD or equivalent experience in computational biology or bioinformatics
- Extensive programming experience, preferably Python
- Experience with pipelining tools like snakemake and **nextflow** preferred

- Strong foundations in statistics and machine learning
- Experience with HPCs or cloud computing in e.g., AWS or GCP
- Familiarity with standard bioinformatics pipeline development such as **NextFlow** or Snakemake

Desired Qualifications

- Master or PhD in computational biology or bioinformatics
- Proficient in at least one programming language (Python, R, Java) and database development using MongoDB, API development, UI development
- Experience performing microbial genomic analysis.
- Experience in pipeline construction with Snakemake or **Nextflow**.
- Experience with containerization (e.g. Docker, Singularity), cloud computing (e.g. AWS), data science (analysis and interpretation of data), SCRUM and Agile software development.

- Experience working with containers (e.g., Docker) and workflow management software (e.g. **Nextflow**, WDL, or Snakemake)

Hello World

A minimalist example of Nextflow syntax

- **process sayHello {}**
wraps a command we want to run
- **workflow {}**
is where you write the plumbing logic
- **sayHello()**
is how you tell Nextflow to actually run that step

```
process sayHello {  
    output:  
        stdout  
        ""  
        echo 'Hello World!'  
        ""  
}  
  
workflow {  
    sayHello()  
}
```


Nextflow run

Straightforward CLI syntax

```
hello-nextflow -> nextflow run hello-world.nf
Nextflow 24.08.0-edge is available - Please consider updating your version to it
```

```
N E X T F L O W ~ version 24.02.0-edge
```

```
| Launching `hello-world.nf` [pedantic_liskov] DSL2 - revision: f9af43455e
```

```
executor > local (1)
[6d/92c542] sayHello | 1 of 1 ✓
```

```
hello-nextflow -> █
```

(Tip: add *-resume* to automatically resume running from point of change or point of failure)

Hello World redux

Adding a few refinements for handling inputs and outputs

- **publishDir** and **output**
tells Nextflow where to write the outputs
- **params**
allows you to pass in command-line options
- **input**
handles the input variable(s)
- **Channel.of()**
loads the input(s) into a channel

```
params.greeting = "Hello World!"

process sayHello {

    publishDir 'results', mode: 'copy'

    input:
        val greeting

    output:
        path "output.txt"

    """
    echo '$greeting' > "output.txt"
    """
}

workflow {

    // create a channel for inputs
    greeting_ch = Channel.of(params.greeting)

    // emit a greeting
    sayHello(greeting_ch)
}
```


Nextflow channels

Shuttling inputs and outputs between processes, handling parallelization implicitly

If you load multiple elements into the channel → Nextflow will parallelize execution automatically

(Caveat: output order is not guaranteed)

Hello World redux 2

Adding a second step to the pipeline

- **process convertToUpper**
converts text input to uppercase
- **convertToUpper(sayHello.out)**
runs the second process on the output of the first process
- **Channel.of('Hello', 'Bonjour', 'Holà')**
loads multiple elements into the input channel

```
> process sayHello { ...
}

process convertToUpper {
  input:
    path input_file

  output:
    path "UPPER-${input_file}"

  """
  cat '$input_file' | tr '[a-z]' '[A-Z]' > UPPER-${input_file}
  """
}

workflow {

  // create a channel for inputs
  greeting_ch = Channel.of('Hello', 'Bonjour', 'Holà')

  // emit a greeting
  sayHello(greeting_ch)

  // convert the greeting to uppercase
  convertToUpper(sayHello.out)
}
```


Result

Build and maintain portable, reproducible pipelines

02.

nf-core tools
and best practices

Phil Ewels

nf-core co-founder
PM for Open Source

nf-core

A community effort to collect a curated set of analysis pipelines built using Nextflow.

VIEW
PIPELINES

For facilities

Highly optimised pipelines with excellent reporting. Validated releases ensure reproducibility.

For users

Portable, documented and easy to use workflows. Pipelines that you can trust.

For developers

Companion templates and tools help to validate your code and simplify common tasks.

nf-core is published in Nature Biotechnology!

[Nat Biotechnol 38, 276–278 \(2020\).](#)

nf-core resources

108

Pipelines

nf-core

Ready-to-use best-practice
pipelines written in Nextflow

Powering impactful research

nature cell biology

Article | [Open Access](#) | Published: 12 May 2022

Sox2 levels regulate the chromatin occupancy of WNT mediators in epiblast progenitors responsible for vertebrate body formation

Robert Blassberg, Harshil Patel, Thomas Watson, Mina Gouti, Vicki Metzis, M. Joaquina Delás & James Briscoe

Nature Cell Biology 24, 633–644 (2022) | [Cite this article](#)

nf-core/
rnaseq

nf-core/
atacseq

nf-core/
chipseq

nature communications

Article | [Open Access](#) | Published: 08 October 2021

Characterisation of tumour microenvironment remodelling following oncogene inhibition in preclinical studies using imaging mass cytometry

Febe van Maldegem, Karishma Valand, Megan Cole, Harshil Patel, Mihaela Angelova, Sareena Rana, Emma Colliver, Katey Enfield, Nouridine Bah, Gavin Kelly, Victoria Siu Kwan Tsang, Edurne Mugarza, Christopher Moore, Philip Hobson, Dina Levi, Miriam Molina-Arcas, Charles Swanton & Julian Downward

Nature Communications 12, Article number: 5906 (2021) | [Cite this article](#)

nf-core/
imcyto

bioRxiv

THE PREPRINT SERVER FOR BIOLOGY

A systematic benchmark of Nanopore long read RNA sequencing for transcript level analysis in human cell lines

Ying Chen, Nadia M. Davidson, Yuk Kei Wan, Harshil Patel, Fei Yao, Hwee Meng Low, Christopher Hendra, Laura Watten, Andre Sim, Chelsea Sawyer, Viktoriia Iakovleva, Puay Leng Lee, Lixia Xin, Hui En Vanessa Ng, Jia Min Loo, Xuewen Ong, Hui Qi Amanda Ng, Jiaxu Wang, Wei Qian Casslynn Koh, Suk Teah Polly Poon, Dominik Stanojevic, Hoang-Dai Tran, Kok Hao Edwin Lim, Shen Yun Toh, Philip Andrew Ewels, Huck-Hui Ng, N. Gopalakrishna Iyer, Alexandre Thiery, Wee Joo Ching, Leilei Chen, Ramanuj DasGupta, Mile Sikić, Yun-Shen Chan, Boon Ooi Patrick Tan, Yue Wan, Wai Leong Tam, Qiang Yu, Chia Chuan Khor, Torsten Wüstefeld, Ploy N. Pratanwanich, Michael I. Love, Wee Siong Sho Goh, Sarah B. Ng, Alicia Oshlack, Jonathan Göke, SG-NEx consortium

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.04.21.440736>

nf-core/
nanoseq

NAR Genomics and Bioinformatics

nf-core/mag: a best-practice pipeline for metagenome hybrid assembly and binning

Sabrina Krakau, Daniel Straub, Hadrien Gourlé, Gisela Gabernet, Sven Nahnsen

NAR Genomics and Bioinformatics, Volume 4, Issue 1, March 2022, lqac007,

<https://doi.org/10.1093/nargab/lqac007>

Published: 02 February 2022

nf-core/
mag

bioRxiv

THE PREPRINT SERVER FOR BIOLOGY

MICA: A multi-omics method to predict gene regulatory networks in early human embryos

Gregorio Alanis-Lobato, Thomas E. Bartlett, Qiulin Huang, Claire Simon, Afshan McCarthy, Kay Elder, Phil Snell, Leila Christie, Kathy Niakan

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.02.03.527081>

nf-core/
rnaseq

DIaproteomics: A Multifunctional Data Analysis Pipeline for Data-Independent Acquisition Proteomics and Peptidomics

Leon Bichmann*, Shubham Gupta, George Rosenberger, Leon Kuchenbecker, Timo Sachsenberg, Phil Ewels, Oliver Alka, Julianus Pfeuffer, Oliver Kohlbacher, and Hannes Röst

Cite this: *J. Proteome Res.* 2021, 20, 7, 3758–3766

Publication Date: June 21, 2021

<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.1c00123>

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nf-core/
diaproteomics

nf-core resources and tools

Pick and choose which components you need

Pipelines

>100 pipelines and a base template

Subworkflows

60 subworkflows

Modules

>>1,200 modules

Linting

Choose conventions to test for consistency

Schema

Validation, channels and user interface

Tooling

Development and deployment

nf-core pipeline components

Pipeline

Pipeline parameters

Resource requests

Tool arguments

Input channels

Subworkflow

Channels

Pipeline logic

Module

Module

Module

Pipelines based on the nf-core template

Participate

Seminars, training, hackathons, and more

- Bytesize seminars
- Training
- Hackathons
- Social media
- Blogs
- Community Slack
- Documentation
- Swag
- Mentorships

03.

Getting **started**, getting **help** and engaging with the **community**

Self-service online training

Nextflow Training

Welcome to the Nextflow community training portal!

These training materials are open source and free to use for anyone. They are hosted in a [GitHub repository](#) along with example scripts and development configuration.

Whilst you can follow the materials any time, you'll probably get the most out of them by joining an organized training event. Free online events are organized regularly with the nf-core community, see the [nf-core events page](#) for more.

We have several workshops available on this website - find the one that's right for you!

 [Gitpod](#) [Open in Gitpod](#)

Pre-loaded Gitpod environment

The screenshot displays the Gitpod IDE interface. On the left, the Explorer panel shows the workspace structure under 'GITPOD-WS (WORKSPACE)'. The 'hello-nextflow' directory is expanded, showing files like '.nextflow', 'data', 'scripts', 'work', and log files. The main editor shows the 'hello-world.nf' file with the following content:

```
hello-nextflow > X hello-world.nf
1 process sayHello {
2
3     output:
4         stdout
5
6         """"
7         echo 'Hello World!'
8         """"
9 }
10
```

Below the editor, the Terminal panel shows the execution of the pipeline:

```
nf-training -> cd ../hello-nextflow/
hello-nextflow -> nextflow run hello-world.nf
Nextflow 24.08.0-edge is available - Please consider updating your version to it

NEXTFLOW ~ version 24.02.0-edge

| Launching `hello-world.nf` [furious_laLande] DSL2 - revision: f9af43455e

executor > local (1)
[88/86fa46] sayHello | 1 of 1 ✓

hello-nextflow -> |
```

The status bar at the bottom indicates the current branch is 'master*', the file encoding is UTF-8, and the layout is U.S. Other icons include Spell, Ports (34725), and Prettier.

Get help at community.seqera.io

🗨️ 🔍 👤 ☰

Open Forum for Open Science

Community support for scientific OSS and collaborative bioinformatics discussion

Categories ▾ Tags ▾ Categories Latest New (4) Unread (1) Top 🔧 ▾ New Topic

See 1 new or updated topic

Latest

	Enabling <code>`-resume`</code> and <code>`-log`</code> on AWS Batch • Ask for help aws	1	2h
	☑ Plot.show() in Quarto notebook after if statement is not showing Ask for help multiqc	1	1d
	Using conda environments in singularity containers with nextflow Ask for help nextflow singularity	4	1d

- 📁 Topics •
- 👤 My Posts
- 🏆 Leaderboard
- 📄 Review
- 🔧 Admin
- 📅 Upcoming events
- ⋮ More
- ▾ Categories
 - 🔴 Ask for help •
 - 🔵 Show & Tell
 - 🟢 Tips & Tricks

Nextflow users by country

Nextflow users by population size

Community engagement initiatives

Ambassadors Program

Supporting motivated individuals who are active in their community

Travel grants, expenses, training resources

- Engage with the community
- Organize local events (meetups, trainings)
- Present work done with Nextflow at conferences
- Share experience through blogs and social media

Apply to join at <https://www.nextflow.io/ambassadors.html>

Next call (for 2025) will close in December

Nextflow Training: Bridging online learning with in-person connections

Florian Wuenemann
Bioinformatics Engineer
at Seqera

Kübra Narci
Bioinformatician
and Bioinformatic Workflows
Engineer for GHGA in the
Workflows workstream

Learn more

<https://www.nextflow.io/blog/2024/training-local-site.html>

Community engagement initiatives

Ambassadors Program

Supporting motivated individuals who are active in their community

Travel grants, expenses, training resources

Outreach to Organizations

Providing resources to core facilities and educators to help them achieve their mission

Training resources, staff training

- Reduce duplication of effort re: training researchers and students
- Empower support staff and educators
- Develop lesson plans, videos etc. based on needs

New modular workshops to facilitate learning

- Introduction to Nextflow
- Leveraging nf-core
- Testing with nf-test
- Troubleshooting

Community engagement initiatives

Ambassadors Program

Supporting motivated individuals who are active in their community

Travel grants, expenses, training resources

Outreach to Organizations

Providing resources to core facilities and educators to help them achieve their mission

Training resources, staff training

Seqera Cloud Academic Program

Providing free Pro-level access to Seqera Cloud for qualifying academics

- **Seqera Cloud Platform** is a collaborative platform designed to maximize research productivity by enabling data analysis at scale.
- The Academic Program provides free access to the **Professional tier** of the Cloud Platform for researchers, educators and their students, at qualifying institutions.
- Community-based support at <https://community.seqera.io/tags/c/help/37/platform>

The screenshot shows the Seqera community forum interface. At the top left is the Seqera logo. On the top right, there are links for 'Sign Up' and 'Log In', along with search and menu icons. Below the header, there are navigation filters: 'Ask For Help' (with a red square icon), 'Platform', and 'All'. Sorting options 'Latest' and 'Top' are also present. The main content area displays a list of help topics with columns for 'Topic', 'Replies', 'Views', and 'Activity'. Two topics are visible: 'Adding non-aws S3 bucket in seqera platform' and 'Azure Batch: is there a way to specify Spot Instances'. A right-hand sidebar contains navigation links for 'Topics', 'Leaderboard', 'Upcoming e...', 'More', 'Categories', 'All categories', and 'Tags'.

Topic	Replies	Views	Activity
Adding non-aws S3 bucket in seqera platform Ask for help platform aws	1	167	33m
Azure Batch: is there a way to specify Spot Instances Ask for help platform azure-batch	2	136	10d

04.

Seqera **Platform:**

Where Nextflow **runs best**

Where Nextflow runs best.

Limitless scale.

Unprecedented speed & scale with automated resource management

No compromises on cost or performance.

Fusion delivers faster & cheaper workloads vs traditional S3

Reduce long-term storage costs by ~76%

community | showcase

- Launchpad
- Runs
- Actions
- Datasets
- Data Explorer
- Data Studios
- Compute Environments
- Credentials
- Secrets
- Participants

Launchpad

Launch a run by selecting one of the available pipelines below. Pipelines contain a configured workflow repository, compute environment, and launch parameters.

Showing 1-15 of 15 Sort by: Recently updated Search...

community | showcase

- Launchpad
- Runs**
- Actions
- Datasets
- Data Explorer
- Data Studios
- Compute Environments
- Credentials
- Secrets
- Participants

Runs

Monitor and inspect the details of workflow executions in your workspace.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Search workflow...		Search		Delete selected				
<input type="checkbox"/>	romantic_brown nextflow-io/hello		gvarma	Sep 19, 2024, 7:23 AM	cancelled after 34s				
<input type="checkbox"/>	sleepy_nightingale nextflow-io/hello		gvarma	Sep 19, 2024, 7:22 AM	succeeded after 3m				
<input type="checkbox"/>	fabulous_mayer nf-core/rnaseq		rnaseq		lukas-heumos1	Sep 18, 2024, 10:35 PM	succeeded after 12m		
<input type="checkbox"/>	hopeful_brahmagupta nf-core/viralrecon		zig-tan1	Sep 18, 2024, 4:28 PM	succeeded after 12m				
<input type="checkbox"/>	test-run nf-core/viralrecon		zig-tan1	Sep 18, 2024, 12:46 PM	succeeded after 16m				

< View Workflow Run

✓ **admiring_ramanujan** nf-core/rnaseq

rnaseq

Command line Parameters Configuration Datasets Execution log Reports

```
nextflow run 'https://github.com/nf-core/rnaseq'  
-name admiring_ramanujan  
-params-file 'https://api.cloud.seqera.io/ephemeral/fuxkA8XmeGz-od0Yxq5DCw.yaml'  
-with-tower 'https://api.tower.nf'  
-r 3.14.0  
-profile test
```

General

id 1dRrGuj6Dpq6J4
admiring_ramanujan
2024-09-12 17:59:21
b89fac32650aac886fcd9ee77e00612a1d77066 (3.14.0)
e0338f81-755a-4ff2-b49f-ffa6f3c93f20
evanfloden
s3://nf-tower-bucket/scratch/1dRrGuj6Dpq6J4

Status

0 pending	0 submitted	0 running
0 cached	192 succeeded	0 failed

Seqera Pipelines

Find the pipelines you need for your research

- Collection of curated high-quality pipelines from public repositories
- Help researchers **finding and testing** the pipelines they need, fast
- Strict inclusion criteria
 - Publicly accessible test data
 - Actively maintained
 - Guaranteed to run on the 1st try
- Pipeline catalog is constantly expanding

<https://seqera.io/pipelines>

Seqera Containers

Build what you need, when you need it

- On-demand container provisioning
- Build custom environments with few clicks
 - Instant URI for custom environments
 - Docker or Singularity image format
 - Multiple architecture support
- Ensure reproducibility of your analyses
 - Pipelines
 - Interactive environments
 - Anything that can use containers

<https://seqera.io/containers>

Seqera Data Explorer

Visualize, search, and manage data across cloud providers

- Move the compute to the data
 - No need to copy large datasets
 - Browse & interact directly
- Avoid multiple cloud-specific CLIs when staging or manipulating data
- Automatically connect to buckets using workspace credentials
- Monitor pipeline work directories & intermediate files at runtime
- Preview & download pipeline input and output data

Generally Available

Seqera Data Studios

Secure notebooks and interactive applications, with your data, in your environment

- Launch Jupyter Labs, RStudio, and VSCode within Seqera Platform
- One-click provisioning & management
- Seamless colocation of data & analysis
- Perform downstream tertiary analyses (EDA; machine learning; interactive dashboards)
- Debug pipelines by connecting interactive tools to results and work directories

Public Preview

05.

Upcoming **events**

Get ready for the

X SUMMIT 2024

Barcelona Oct 28 - Nov 1

Pioneering the future of science through
community-driven innovation in software.

More info at: summit.nextflow.io

06.

Q&A